

QUIZ**LAST NAME: EMRICH****FIRST NAME: LINA****PROGRAM CODE: MMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice for mac on macOS Mojave

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **A style guide provides guidance on numerous matters regarding writing. Which of the following is NOT something a style guide would offer guidance on?**
 - Spelling.
 - Research method.¹**
 - Voice preference.
 - Font size.
2. **Which of the following sentences uses the comma incorrectly?**
 - The receptionist said, “You have until tomorrow to hand in your application form.”
 - Tofu, a food created from soymilk, is commonly consumed across Asia.

¹ Euclid University, *ACA-401 COURSEPACK PERIOD 1* (Euclid University: 2015), 52-53, accessed September 11, 2019, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-1/>.

I made a controversial proposal at the meeting, my coworkers accepted it without objection.²

The white, well-tempered cat leapt on my lap and fell sleep.

3. **Which of the following sources is a primary source?**

A political commentary.

An encyclopedia.

A textbook.

An interview.³

4. **According to Turabian, at which point in writing should a writer construct their first hypothesis?**

Before or during the research stage.⁴

When they start their first draft.

When the report is almost finished.

After the report is finished.

5. **In which of the following circumstances is a citation not required?**

² Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*, 4th ed. (Wilmington: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 403-406.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., 8th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 24.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 21.

- When quoting an interview answer.
- When providing research data from a journal article.
- When summarizing the ideas of a book.
- When stating a fact which is considered common sense.⁵**

6. **When citing an online source, what information is NOT required for correct citation?**

- Identifying information such as author or website title.
- Access date.
- Publication date.⁶**
- Uniform Resource Locator (URL).

7. **Which of the following phrases is against the European Commission's English Style Guide?**

- 5 international students were admitted in 2006, 8 in 2007, and 12 in 2008.
- The city accepted 4 hundred refugees last month.⁷**
- The minimum wage is nine euros.
- Most companies adopted a 40-hour week.

⁵ Euclid University, *ACA-401 COURSEPACK PERIOD 4* (Euclid University: 2015), 75, accessed October 14, 2019, <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/Y1JXVLgPv0/>.

⁶ Turabian, 118.

⁷ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. (European Commission: 2011), 28-30, accessed October 24, 2019, <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/xitMjHAGfJ/>.

8. **While reading a book by Jones, you learn about a useful research done by Smith and wish to cite that research in your own paper. However, you searched through all the journals you have access to but could not locate the article by Smith. According to the Harvard Rule of Style, how should you cite the research done by Smith, which you could only find through the book by Jones?**
- Cite Jones in both the in-text citation and the reference list.
 - Cite Smith in both the in-text citation and the reference list.
 - Cite both Smith and Jones in the in-text citation and the reference list.
 - Cite both Smith and Jones in the in-text citation but only Jones in the reference list.⁸**
9. **Which of the following indicates that an online source may be unreliable?**
- It strongly advocates for privatizing prisons.⁹**
 - It is sponsored by the World Health Organization.
 - It was updated 2 months ago.
 - It is a supplement to the British Medical Journal.
10. **Which of the following sentences is grammatically incorrect?**
- Neither my mother nor my father has blue eyes.
 - Sara and her friend enjoys jogging in the park.¹⁰**

⁸ Euclid University, *ACA-401 COURSEPACK PERIOD 4*, 93.

⁹ Turabian, 28-29.

¹⁰ Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer, 100.

- Each of the piano players has long fingers.
- Everyone in my class is taking their laptops to school.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.